

DEVELOPMENT AND CHALLENGES OF INCLUSIVE AND INTEGRATED EDUCATION

Shankaramurthy H.K. & Dr. Sushma R

Alva's College of Education, Moodbidri, D.K. (Dist.)

Email Id: shankaramurthyhk.hk@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Inclusive education is a set of values, principals and practices that seeks more effective and meaningful education for all students, regardless of whether they have exceptionality labels Or not. Inclusive education means that all students attend and are welcomed by their neighborhood schools in age-appropriate, regular classes and are supported to learn, contribute and participate in all aspects of the life of the school. Inclusive education is carried out in a common learning environment; that is, an educational setting where students from different backgrounds and with different abilities learn together in an inclusive environment. Common learning environments are used for the majority of the students' regular instruction hours and may include classrooms, libraries, gym, performance theatres, music rooms, cafeterias, playgrounds and the local community. The term inclusion refers to an approach wherein students with special need spend most or all of their time with non-disabled students Inclusive classrooms might contain several students with special needs who are mainstreamed full time into the general classroom, or one or two students who spend time each day in both a special education classroom and a general classroom. Integrated schools bring together children and adults from different religion, caste and class in each school. The schools strive to achieve a religious balance of pupils, teachers and governors and acknowledge and respect the cultural diversity they represent. Integrated schools educate children in an environment where self-esteem and independence are developed as priorities. Self-respect and respect for others are strongly encouraged. The integrated ethos is nurtured to ensure inclusion of people from different religions, cultures, genders, abilities and socio-economic backgrounds. Integrated education encourages open-minded attitudes among pupils as well as building the confidence and ability to question, observe, listen and make informed decisions.

Keywords: Inclusive and integrated Education, Disability, Cultural diversity

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Introduction:

India has made impressive economic gains in the last few decades and currently has the 4th largest economy in terms of purchasing power parity. Despite this improvement, more than 260 million people in India live in poverty. The reciprocity of poverty producing disability, and disability resulting in poverty creates unique challenges for the integrated education movement in India. A number of strategies are presented to address the current challenges that Indian administrators and educators face in the move towards more integrated education.

Challenges to implement inclusive and integrated education:

The challenge of poverty associated with disability:

With an estimated 1,027 million people, India is the world's second most populated country. It has 17 % of the global population and 20 % of the world's out-of-school children. Despite impressive gains in the last few decades India still has more than 260 million people living in poverty. However, motivating poor families, with all the associated costs to send their child to school, is proving to be a big challenge.

The challenge of modifying deeply held attitudes:

Attitudes of the non-disabled are proving to be a major barrier in the social integration of persons with disabilities. "The more severe and visible the deformity is, the greater is the fear of contagion, hence the attitudes of aversion and segregation towards the crippled" Such attitudes reinforced by religious institutions may militate against any attempts to include students with disabilities into regular schools.

Dissemination and public education:

People, including parents and school personnel, are largely unaware of the full intent of the recent legislation passed by Indian Parliament. A large number of school personnel are also not aware of funding available to include students with disabilities in regular schools.

The challenge of providing adequate levels of training to key stakeholders:

The majority of school personnel in India are not trained to design and implement educational programs for students with disabilities in regular schools. Most teacher training programs in India do not have a unit on Disability Studies. The universities, which do cover some aspects of special education in their teacher training programs, fail to train teachers adequately to work in integrated settings.

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Inadequate resources:

The majority of schools in India are poorly designed and few are equipped to meet the unique needs of students with disabilities. The lack of disability friendly transportation services and accessible buildings are considered by some to be far greater problems than social prejudice and negative attitudes. Both the Central and State governments will have to provide increased resources to this aspect of education to ensure successful implementation of integrated practices in schools.

Possible strategies to address some of the challenges:

Training of teachers:

If integrated education is to become a reality in India, then the training of teachers has to become a top priority. The educational authorities in India may adopt a policy of training one teacher from each school or a cluster of schools.

Need to design innovative system of training:

Several authors have cautioned that India will not be able to successfully implement integrated educational services unless regular school educators are trained at mass scale. comments on this situation as follows: "the number of persons who need training is very large and the conventional training methods cannot simply meet the requirements." Therefore, there is a need to design some innovative models to train educators at mass level.

Need for collaboration between different ministries:

Different ministries in India administer various services for persons with disabilities (Alur, 2001). For example, while "integrated education" is the responsibility of Ministry of Human Resource Development, education in special schools is the responsibility of Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment.

Involve NGO's in implementing integrated education programs:

There are more than one million NGO's workings in India. Although not all of them are working in the education sector, a large number still provide educational services to children with disabilities. These organizations can play a significant role in implementing integrated education.

Establish an alternate system of examination:

Most school educators in India are concerned that integration of students with disabilities would result in lowering school standards because these students won't be able to pass exams .This seems

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to be a genuine concern of teachers because it can influence their promotion.

School-university partnership:

The multilingual, multi-cultural and multi-religious nature of India is often cited as a challenge in implementing any educational reforms. Local universities in each of the States and Union Territories may play a significant role in overcoming this challenge.

Principles and necessary resources:

- Adequate supports and services for the student
- Well-designed individualized education programs.
- Professional development for all teachers involved, general and special educators alike
- Time for teachers to plan, meet, create, and evaluate the students together
- Reduced class size based on the severity of the student needs
- Professional skill development in the areas of cooperative learning, peer tutoring, adaptive curriculum
- Collaboration between parents or guardians, teachers or para educators, specialists, administration, and outside agencies.
- Sufficient funding so that schools will be able to develop programs for students based on student need instead of the availability of funding.

In principle, several factors can determine the success of integrated classrooms:

- Family-school partnerships and Collaboration between general and special educators
- Well-constructed plans that identify specific accommodations, modifications, and goals for each student
- Coordinated planning and communication between "general" and "special needs" staff
- Integrated service delivery
- Leadership of teachers and administrators

Teachers use a number of techniques to help build classroom communities:

- Using games designed to build community
- Involving students in solving problems
- Sharing songs and books that teach community

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- Openly dealing with individual differences by discussion
- Teaching students to look for ways to help each other
- Encouraging students to take the role of teacher and deliver instruction .
- Focusing on the strength of a student with special needs
- Organize student desk in groups
- Create a self and welcoming environment
- Design a multi-faced curriculum
- Communicate regular with parents and/or caregivers
- Seek support from other special education teachers.

Inclusionary practices are commonly utilized by using the following team-teaching models:

In this model, the content teacher will deliver the lesson and the special education teacher will assist student’s individual needs and enforce classroom management as needed.

- **One teach, one observe:**

In this model, the teacher with the most experience in the content will deliver the lesson and the other teacher will float or observe. This model is commonly used for data retrieval during IEP observations or Functional Behaviour Analysis.

- **Station teaching:**

In this model, the room is divided into stations in which the students will visit with their small groups. Generally, the content teacher will deliver the lesson in his/her group, and the special education teacher will complete a review or adapted version of the lesson with the students.

- **Parallel teaching:**

In this model, one half of the class is taught by the content teacher and one half is taught by the special education teacher. Both groups are being taught the same lesson, just in a smaller group.

- **Alternative teaching:**

In this method, the content teacher will teach the lesson to the class, while the special education teacher will teach a small group of students an alternative lesson.

- **Team teaching:**

Both teachers share the planning, teaching, and supporting equally. This is the traditional method, and often the most successful co-teaching model.

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Key Features of Inclusive and integrated Education:

- Generally, inclusive education will be successful if these important features and practices are followed:
- Accepting unconditionally all children into regular classes and the life of the school.
- Providing as much support to children, teachers and classrooms as necessary to ensure that all children can participate in their schools and classes.
- Looking at all children at what they can do rather than what they cannot do.
- Teachers and parents have high expectations of all children.
- Developing education goals according to each child’s abilities. This means that children do not need to have the same education goals in order to learn together in regular classes.
- Designing schools and classes in ways that help children learn and achieve to their fullest potential.
- Having strong leadership for inclusion from school principals and other administrators.
- Having teachers who have knowledge about different ways of teaching so that children with various abilities and strengths can learn together.

The importance of Inclusive and integrated Education:

- All children are able to be part of their community and develop a sense of belonging and become better prepared for life in the community as children and adults.
- It provides better opportunities for learning. Children with varying abilities are often better motivated when they learn in classes surrounded by other children.
- The expectations of all the children are higher. Successful inclusion attempts to develop an individual’s strengths and gifts.
- It allows children to work on individual goals while being with other students their own age.
- It encourages the involvement of parents in the education of their children and the activities of their local schools.
- It fosters a culture of respect and belonging. It also provides the opportunity to learn about and accept individual differences.
- It provides all children with opportunities to develop friendships with one another. Friendships provide role models and opportunities for growth.

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Conclusion:

Inclusive and integrated practice can be defined as attitudes and methods that ensure all learners can access mainstream education. Everyone works to make sure all learners feel welcome and valued and that they get the right support to help them develop their talents and achieve their goals. When education is truly inclusive it can actually benefit all learners, not only Disabled learners.

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